

'READ LIKE ME' TO INCREASE THE READING COMPREHENSION OF GRADE IV STRUGGLING READERS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the impacts of 'Read Like Me' to increase the reading comprehension of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School. It was a four-week study; three times a week implementation every Monday, Tuesday and Wednesday. It was an experimental research wherein the researchers implemented 'Read Like Me' to increase the reading comprehension of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School and determine how they influenced the reading comprehension of pupils. The study sample composed of 21 Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School who have shown difficulty when it comes to reading comprehension. The research instruments include pre-test, post-test and a daily tracking form to track the participant's words correct per minute (WCPM). Based on the data gathered, the study showed that the mean pretest score of the Grade IV struggling readers before the intervention was 10.71 (SD= 4.43) indicating a lower level of reading comprehension. As a result of the posttest, the pupils got a mean score of 15.62 (SD= 3.98), showed an improvement in their reading comprehension. Moreover, it was revealed that there is a significant difference in the scores of the pupils before and after the 'Read Like Me' intervention. It indicates that repeated reading intervention had a positive impact on the pupil's reading comprehension.

Keywords: *reading, reading comprehension, repeated reading, struggling readers and words correct per minute (WCPM)*

INTRODUCTION

Learning to read was one of the most important skills that children should master. According to WETA Public Broadcasting (2020), reading provided a lot of benefits which include stimulation of the brain, increased imagination and curiosity, decreased stress and anxiety, and children building self-confidence. As stated in DEPED Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019, there was a need to strengthen the reading proficiency of every learner and to nurture the philosophy of reading which a requisite skill in all content areas is. In response to this DepEd Memo, the Division of Dasmariñas released DepEd Memorandum No. 181, s. 2021. It was stated that the Division continuously envisions making every learner a reader even amid this pandemic as indicated in the Division Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). According to Romig and Jetton (2023); due to the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers are left to transition from face-to-face instruction to the blended mode of learning (modular and online formats) without much of evidence on how to do so effectively. School closures lead teachers to prepare and implement programs to create new approaches to evidence-based reading intervention. As stated by Lee and Yoon (2017) in their meta-analysis of repeated reading interventions and included peer-reviewed journal articles and dissertations. Repeated reading interventions were more successful with elementary pupils than with secondary pupils, for primary reading levels than with secondary reading levels, with passage preview (modelling) than without, and with non-transfer passages than with transfer passages.

Research Questions

This research focused on the impacts of ‘Read Like Me’ to increase the reading comprehension of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School.

Specifically, it sought to answers the following questions:

1. What is the mean pre-test score of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School before the ‘Read Like Me’ intervention?
2. What is the mean post-test score of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School after the ‘Read Like Me’ intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference between the reading comprehension of Grade IV struggling readers before and after the ‘Read Like Me’ intervention?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This type of research was an experimental research. The vital aspect of experimental research is that researchers control and influence the conditions that determine the events in which they are interested, propose an intervention, and measure the difference that it makes. So, in this study, the researchers implemented ‘Read Like Me’ to increase the reading comprehension of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School and determine how they influenced the reading comprehension of

pupils. *Subject and Respondents of the Study.* The sample of the population of this study stood at 21 Grade IV struggling readers; giving a total of 21 respondents. *Sampling Techniques.* The method of purposive sampling was used in the study. The participants of this study were the Grade IV pupils in Linawan Integrated School who have shown difficulty when it comes to reading comprehension based on Phil-IRI curriculum-based screening indicating below-grade level reading comprehension. *Research Instrumentation.* The researchers obtained individual reading passages from the educational website of DIBELS-ORF or Dynamic Indicators of Basic Early Literacy Skills for the Grade IV Reading Fluency passages (University of Oregon, Center on Teaching and Learning, 2018). Additionally, researchers developed data collection documents such as a pre-test, post-test, and a daily tracking form to track the participant's words correct per minute (WCPM) wherein was validated by several experts.

The WCPM Daily Tracking form was used to record each session date, a number of words read correctly, the number of words in a text, the percentage range, and the reading level of participants. Additionally, a 20-multiple comprehension questions were made for pre-test and post-test. It was based on the reading passages from DIBELS-ORF used during the intervention process. Furthermore, the pupils were required to read each question and encircle the letter of the best answer. There were four (4) choices in each item wherein the pupils must choose the best answer for each question. The percentage of correct words circled by each pupil on the multiple-choice questions was recorded as a measure of comprehension. Also, a pilot testing of those research instruments happened. *Statistical Treatment of the Data.* Descriptive statistics such as mean were used in analyzing the data generated from the pre-test and post-test of the intervention. Furthermore, the Dependent T-Test or Paired Sample T-Test was used to determine if there is a significant difference in the reading performance of Grade IV struggling readers before and after the 'Read Like Me' intervention.

RESULTS

Table 1. The pretest results of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School before the 'Read Like Me' intervention

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Pre-test Scores	21	3	18	10.71	4.429
Valid N (listwise)	21				

Table 2. The posttest results of Grade IV struggling readers in Linawan Integrated School after the 'Read Like Me' intervention

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Post-test Scores	21	6	20	15.62	3.981
Valid N (listwise)	21				

Table 3. Paired Sample T-Test result

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Post-test Scores Pre-test Scores	4.905	4.312	.941	2.942	6.867	5.213	20	.000

DISCUSSION

As presented in Table 1, it showed that the highest score got by the Grade IV pupils was 18 and the lowest score was 3 (M= 10.71; SD= 4.43) before the 'Read Like Me' intervention happened. This indicates that the pupils have a lower level of reading comprehension. Most pupils scored in the *Frustration* oral reading level wherein the pupils have difficulty in understanding their reading materials. This supported the study of Kudan, H. & Kyol, H. (2018) which states that errors in reading affect the level of comprehension negatively, as they result in pupils losing their understanding.

As revealed in Table 2, it showed that the highest score got by the Grade IV pupils was 20 and the lowest score was 6 (M= 15.62; SD= 3.98). This indicates that there is an increase in the mean score of Grade IV pupils during the post-test. It showed an improvement in their reading comprehension. Thus, the pupils scored in the *Instructional* and *Independent* level of comprehension wherein the pupils can read their own or with the assistance of the teacher. This emphasizes the study of Papadima-Sophocleous and Charalambous (2014) which demonstrates improved results through the assistance of repeated reading to the pupils who are more inclined to read word for word.

As seen in Table 3, a paired sample t-test showed that the performance of students increased after the intervention had been made. There was a significant difference in the scores between the reading comprehension test before (M=10.71, SD = 4.43) and after (M = 15.62, SD = 3.98), $t(20) = 5.213$, $p = 0.000$ the intervention. The differences therefore indicate that the Repeated Reading strategy has a positive impact in raising pupils' comprehension levels. The current finding was similar to Dotson-Shupe's (2017) repeated reading study which showed that the repeated reading strategy was successful in increasing the pupils' comprehension abilities and the participants improved their accuracy when reading orally. In addition, Ates (2017) showed that RR develops pupils' metacognitive reading strategies. There is a significant improvement in reading rate and comprehension of the study's experimental group.

Conclusions

Considering the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The pretest performance of the Grade IV struggling readers were low wherein they fall under the *frustration* oral reading level.
2. As evidenced, the posttest performance of Grade IV struggling readers after the 'Read Like Me' intervention was higher than their pretest performance. This implied that repeated reading intervention uplifted the performance of the pupils and the shift towards higher reading levels.
3. There is an indication that repeated reading improves the reading comprehension of Grade IV struggling readers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. Repeated reading strategy may be used to increase the speed, accuracy and reading comprehension of pupils.
2. The use of error correction, feedback, and progress monitoring influenced the motivation to increase the fluency skills of students. The pupils gained confidence with fluency with each passing week. A higher level of pupil achievement in reading can be achieved by combining the essential components of repeated reading.
3. By lengthening the study's timeline, the research could result in more accurate averages and the effectiveness of repeated reading.
4. As the study had its limits, there were some developments in research needed for the accuracy of this study. This study could be developed by future researchers by conducting the same studies on using the repeated reading intervention focusing on the pupil's reading comprehension.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All the participants were informed about the details of the study. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the pupils could withdraw from the study without any consequences. Furthermore, only the researchers have access to the research data. The researchers respect and protect the confidentiality and privacy of the data and information that will be gathered as required by the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 1017).

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